

THE GRAY JOURNEY: A CASE STUDY IN THE MESSINESS OF DIGITAL PRESERVATION WORKFLOW DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract – Workflow development, much like digital preservation, is not a state that is achieved, but a continuous process looking for efficiencies, without sacrificing authenticity, and learning from our mistakes, while discovering and developing better ways of doing things. Although mileposts are achieved along this journey, it is not complete, nor is it without mishaps. It is a messy process.

Accompany Ohio State on its journey to develop a digital preservation repository and workflow for born digital content at scale. This case study will describe the development of the Gray Digital Preservation Repository, associated workflows, mishaps and a side tour along the way, all contextualized within Ohio State's digital preservation environment.

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I. HOW DID WE GET HERE?

To provide context for this journey, the following is a brief history of The Ohio State University's (Ohio State) digital preservation efforts and its ongoing workflow development for the Gray Digital Preservation Repository (Gray Repo). [1] Over the past quarter century, Ohio State's digital preservation efforts have evolved. Initially, its earliest digital preservation efforts began as a member of OhioLiNK, and currently Ohio State's ETDs (electronic

theses and dissertations) are hosted in OhioLiNK's Rosetta digital preservation environment. [2]

By 2005, The Ohio State University Libraries (University Libraries or Libraries) launched its institutional repository, a DSpace instance known as the Knowledge Bank. [3] In light of that fact it had no other digital preservation or exhibits platforms at the time, it became a place to host the University Libraries' digitized content and some born digital accessions, as well as the scholarly output of the University. A separate program, Brittle Books, which has its roots in the 1980s with the microfilming of books that had become too fragile for continued use, had evolved into a digitization effort with the content hosted at the Internet Archive. [4] Brittle book like content, when now digitized, also finds its way into Hathi Trust, which also hosts Ohio State's Google Books digitized content. [5]

In 2012-2013, a team of the University Libraries' personnel that participated in the DigCCur Institute [6] identified a significant gap in the Libraries' preservation activities, leading to the development and articulation of Ohio State's digital preservation framework. [7] Soon thereafter Ohio State launched what became Digital Collections [8], a digital preservation environment, which hosts publicly accessible content that contains mostly digitized materials, although there is some born digital content. Eventually in 2016, the University Libraries

instituted a web archiving program, employing Archive-It [9], as part of Ohio State's digital preservation portfolio.

2017 saw the establishment of digital preservation as an official program at Ohio State with the creation of the digital preservation librarian position, which became a department within the Libraries' Technology and Digital Programs Division in 2023 with the hiring of a digital preservation specialist.

In 2019, the University Libraries refreshed the aforementioned framework, reframing it as its digital preservation ethos [10], along with conducting a digital preservation environmental scan. [11]

Prior to the advent of Digital Collections, and even after its implementation Ohio State stored digital preservation files in a so-called "Dark Archive" which in reality was nothing more than a secure FTP server, albeit with content stored without administrative or intellectual control, nor any active digital preservation monitoring. All this history brings one to the on-going development of Ohio State's Gray Digital Preservation Repository and this case study.

II. WHY TAKE THIS JOURNEY

The Gray Digital Preservation Repository emerged from an initial use case presented by the University Archives (Archives) for their annual collection development efforts. The Archives regularly accrues archival materials to existing, and sometimes new, collections on an annual basis, due to a mandate for collecting University records. Whether the records are analog or born digital, they are typically so voluminous that the Archives' practice is to accession the records, update the finding aid, store them, and provide mediated access. There is minimal descriptive effort, and discovery is incumbent upon the researcher or patron to examine the accession inventories and/or the records themselves.

The University Libraries' existing digital preservation platform, Digital Collections, which inherently requires item level description, was not designed for the ingest and management of digital assets at an accession level for records or objects at scale; hence the need for a second type of digital preservation repository.

As Ohio State began to conceptualize and develop the Gray Repo, the University Libraries recognized that it provides the Libraries not only with a formalized path for the digital preservation of born digital content at scale, but several other content types including restricted materials such as:

- temporal restrictions that often accompany private papers accessioned to units like the Ohio Public Policy Archives;
- digitized and/or born digital content with other rights and access restrictions.

Perhaps, most importantly, the Gray Repo will serve as a replacement for the University Libraries' so-called "Dark Archive" which it has been attempting to replace for at least a decade-and-a-half. [12] While some of the Dark Archive content will eventually find its way into Digital Collections, the vast majority of the millions of digitized files are the preservation files for content that reside in other University Libraries' access repositories, such as the Knowledge Bank, Internet Archive, and Veridian, and will find the next stop on their journey in the Gray Repo.

III. DETERMINING A PATHWAY

A. *Beginning the journey*

The Gray Digital Preservation Repository is the first that the University Libraries has developed at Ohio State since digital preservation became a program, and with digital preservation at its heart. Digital Collections (DC) was initially developed by University Libraries utilizing Fedora and Hydra in response to the decommissioning of a home-grown image management system developed and hosted by the University's College of Arts and Sciences. That system contained a significant amount of University Libraries' digitized content. As such the original name for the DC was the Image Management System (IMS).

Coincidental to its development was an effort to establish a master objects repository to replace the Dark Archive that would house not only images, but other forms of digitized content, as well as born digital accessions. [13] This led to the first migration of an updated version of Fedora and Samvera (the rebranded Hydra). This also led to the rebranding of the IMS to Digital Collections.

Based upon the DC's architecture, the Libraries' own standards for metadata and the human

resources necessary to appropriately process and ingest content into the DC, the University Libraries found itself stumbling on its journey to properly accession, process, ingest and preserve born digital content. Processing a born digital cartoon collection of over 1,000 complex objects that included file format normalizations and manipulations to make sure the items were visibly accessible, proved that the Libraries do not have the bandwidth to conduct this type of accessioning and processing on a regular basis, let alone for collections with potentially tens or hundreds of thousands of digital objects. [14]

B. *Choosing the right vehicle*

Therefore, as the University Libraries began to develop the Gray Digital Preservation Repository in 2021, it provided Ohio State with an opportunity to design a digital preservation first environment. [15] As such, it has developed the Gray Repo with the Open Archival Information System (OAIS) model in mind. [16] Further, this project provided the University Libraries' Applications Development and Operations (AD&O) staff an opportunity to experiment with Fedora 6, as Digital Collections is on a version of Fedora 4; further, this supplied AD&O with the opportunity to become skilled at working with Fedora in a cloud environment on the Amazon Web Services (AWS) platform. [17]

The Gray Digital Preservation Repository allows for curatorial deposit and retrieval, but no direct patron access. As such it is a "dim (or gray) digital preservation archive" as opposed to a "light archive" like the DC which provides public access, or a "dark archive" which only allows custodial access. The Gray Repo is much more akin to a physical archival storage facility where:

- items are stored on shelves in an environmentally regulated and well managed manner;
- items are appropriately described in conformance with accepted standards;
- the public and unvetted personnel are not allowed to wander the stacks.

In the Gray Repo the University Libraries is storing its bagged content—think box on a shelf—in Fedora, a secure digital preservation repository. The bags are managed in a local administrative dashboard, as well as appropriately described in the Libraries' finding aids, while being cross-referenced

to the dashboard; and as the box on the shelf needs to be pulled off the shelf by the curatorial staff, these bags need to be downloaded from Fedora, to be handed over to a researcher or user.

C. *OAIS along the way*

Of the various digital content platforms Ohio State maintains, the design of the Gray Repo comes closest to the Open Archival Information System (OAIS) model. Viewed at a high level, the University Libraries receive a Submission Information Package (SIP) or packages of records from within Ohio State, or from external donors. These SIPs may arrive via Microsoft Teams, other cloud services, email, or on external devices like USB-drives, external hard drives and legacy media. The Libraries conduct a variety of pre-ingest activities, on the materials within the SIP, ultimately preparing the content for ingest into the Gray Repo in the form of a bag, which is then ingested into the Gray Repo's Fedora repository, becoming an Archival Information Package (AIP). Ohio State does not create a separately housed Dissemination Information Package (DIP) with derivative contents; however, a DIP is created as a copy of the AIP when the curatorial staff request a download.

IV. STEPS ALONG THE WORKFLOW ROUTE

Setting up the Fedora environment in AWS was the relatively easy part and was handled by the University Libraries' AD&O staff. However, it took the Digital Preservation Department an extended period of time to identify and test tools, while developing, refining and documenting workflow, before launching the Gray Digital Preservation Repository in January of 2024. The Gray Repo's processing workflow is based upon a combination of a variety of open source and commercial-off-the-shelf tools for pre-ingest analysis, packaging, storage and discovery.

A. *Hardware*

Dating back to the days of the implementation of the Digital Collections platform, the University libraries established a network attached drive (K-Drive) for the storage and handling of its digitized and born digital collections that are actively being processed. The SIPs that are received are placed on the K-Drive in the appropriate collecting area's folder for born digital accessions. Further, the Libraries established two remote desktop workstations with a

higher level of processing power that have all the requisite digital processing software tools loaded. These remote desktops are accessed via a virtual private network (VPN) client.

B. DROID

The first step is to create a manifest of the folders and files that are to be accessioned or migrated utilizing The National Archives' (United Kingdom) DROID (Digital Record Object Identification) tool. [18] DROID is an open-source tool that allows the University Libraries not only to create the manifest of the digital objects within an accession, but establish baseline checksum for each object, as well as conducts a file format analysis that is linked to the PRONOM file format registry. [19] The results created by DROID will be added to the payload in an accession/ingest documentation folder, in addition to being maintained locally for administrative control. This information may be used for appraisal, weeding and/or descriptive purposes, as well as being an initial discovery tool to present researchers prior to having to retrieve the AIP that contains the objects.

C. PII

Being a public institution of higher education, Ohio State must comply with the public records laws of the State of Ohio, as well as United States federal mandates for maintaining records, while protecting personal information that may be contained within. Consequently, both from a cybersecurity point-of-view, together with mitigating the risk of the exposure of personally identifiable information (PII), the University Libraries needs to be able to detect PII within the digital materials it is preserving.

The next phase of the workflow, therefore, is a two-step process for identifying PII. The University Libraries established the need to conduct optical character recognition (OCR) on its imaged content, along with dumb or non-textual PDFs. In the initial tests, the Libraries conducted trials utilizing Adobe Acrobat and ABBYY Fine Reader. For the former, it was initially an appealing solution as the University has enterprise licensing in place and would not need to purchase an additional product. While it worked, it was cumbersome doing it at scale, and created additional PDF files that would ultimately occupy more processing space than desired. ABBYY is another tool that the Libraries already has licensing for, albeit not at an enterprise, unlimited scale. The

results from ABBYY were definitely superior to that of Adobe, however, the University Libraries had never attempted to use ABBYY at the scale it was attempting. In simple testing it was bumping up against licensing limits, let alone if the Libraries were to conduct OCR at scale with tens or hundreds of thousands of files.

The Digital Preservation Department then turned to examining various open-source OCR tools. The preponderance of these tools typically need to be trained, and they work from the command-line. In attempts to keep the workflow simplified and command-line free for the curatorial staff who have to execute the workflow, Digital Preservation turned to the Libraries Head of Digital Initiatives for advice and help with the OCR problem. He was able to develop a simple user interface called Quick PDF OCR that harnesses the power of both the open-source Tesseract [20] and ABBYY to conduct the OCR, providing the University Libraries with .txt files of OCR that can then be examined for PII. The additional benefit is that the .txt files take up far less storage space than an additional PDF that has been through the OCR process.

The University Libraries then use Bulk Extractor [21] to conduct the PII analysis, specifically looking for credit card and social security numbers. The resultant Bulk Extractor reports, if positive, are added to the aforementioned accession/ingest documentation folder.

D. Bagging and Ingest

With the pre-ingest analysis activities complete, The Libraries bag the objects along with the accession/ingest documentation folder using the Library of Congress' Bagger tool. [22] The bag is prepared applying one of the customized profiles that have been created based upon the collecting unit and/or content type. The resultant bag in the form of a .zip file is placed in a designated AWS S3 bucket. This mapped drive has a scripted lambda function attached to it that kicks off when it detects new content in the form of a .zip file, ingesting that content into the Gray Repo instance of Fedora.

When the ingest into Fedora is complete, Fedora generates a checksum and a Fedora ID for the ingested bag. The checksum is presented in the Gray Repo's interface and can be used for quality assurance and provenance purposes. The Fedora ID is also presented in the Gray Repo's interface, as well

as being recorded in a .txt file that is sent back to the appropriate ingest folder in the S3 bucket.

E. Documentation

The Fedora ID text file is copied to the accession/ingest documentation folder to be stored locally, and then that folder is copied to a designated Microsoft Teams folder for future administrative and reference purposes. Various data elements from the documents within that folder are transcribed into the Microsoft Lists Gray Repo Dashboard. Additionally, the Fedora ID is transcribed into Archivists Toolkit to facilitate future retrieval. After fourteen (14) days the appropriate stakeholders are notified of the impending disposal of the .zip bag from the ingest bucket, as well as the original files in the processing environment. Presuming there are no objections, the files are deleted.

F. Retrieval

The Gray Digital Preservation Repository does not have a public user interface for the retrieval of a bag. Discovery happens through review of the University Libraries' finding aids. As previously noted, the finding aid is updated to include the accession of these digital records and lists the corresponding Fedora ID. Similar to requesting a box to be retrieved from the University's archival storage facility, researchers or users after discovering records they would like to view, request retrieval of the digital objects through curatorial staff.

The curatorial staff must log into the Gray Repo via a web browser. Currently there is a rudimentary search interface in which the Fedora ID is copied. Once the appropriate Fedora ID and bag is found, the curatorial staff click the download button, which retrieves the bag. The bag can then be shared through a variety of methods with a researcher or user, including a secure virtual reading room, Teams and other cloud storage solutions, email and/or external media.

V. WHEN YOU ENCOUNTER A MISHAP ALONG THE WAY

A little after six months of ingesting content into the Gray Repo, there was an internal need to retrieve a bag that had audio-visual content. Once downloaded, what should have been a bag with preservation, mezzanine, and streaming files, as well as administrative and metadata documentation, contained only a single preservation file. To further exacerbate the situation, the original processing files

had been deleted from the AWS S3 ingest bucket and the K-Drive processing space, as per the workflow instructions, about a month before the request. What happened? Workflow protocols had been followed – so nothing malicious.

At first, Ohio State thought there might have been corruption in the bagging process. But as Digital Preservation examined the bag information, and ran additional tests with large audio-visual file sets, it determined that it was not Bagger. They also realized, that while Fedora was creating a checksum upon ingest, they had not created a workflow step for generating a checksum for the bagged .zip file prior to ingest that would subsequently be compared to the Fedora generated checksum to verify an authentic transfer and ingest of the bagged content. The University Libraries had completely neglected to create a quality control or assurance step for its workflow, blindly relying on the tools “working” and a payload getting into Fedora. Had they created the checksum prior to ingest, and verified it post-ingest, they would have caught the problem before copies had been disposed.

All told, the Libraries discovered six bags that were corrupted—five with digitized content and one with born digital materials, but all of it audiovisual content. While the six bags should have been of varying sizes, all in excess of 100GB, once in Fedora, they were all approximately 80GB. The Libraries had found the culprit—it was not Bagger and it was not because they were audiovisual files, although their size contributed to the problem—it was the Fedora ingesting process that was timing out at about 80GB.

This mishap exposed several issues. Ohio State had some perceived hard system limit recommendations from its developers, but a review of the workflow indicated that Digital Preservation had never documented and/or communicated that to the curatorial staff, who were conducting the ingesting. This led to successfully pushing well beyond those perceived limits before having several ingest failures at a real hard limit. Further, Digital Preservation plain and simply neglected to add quality assurance or control steps to the workflow that would have immediately identified those failures to completely ingest. Finally, during this deep dive review, the Libraries also discovered missing and/or inaccurate information in the Gray Repo Admin Dashboard.

To ameliorate this and facilitate the creation of quality administrative data, the University Libraries have:

- added quality assurance and control steps pre and post ingest;
- successfully expanded the ability to ingest bags up to 500GB;
- developed a checklist for the curatorial staff to use to make sure the workflow is being adhered to, since it has so many manual, moving parts and is rather voluminous.

Fortunately, for the corrupted bag with born digital content, the Libraries was able to find another whole copy on a testing server and successfully re-ingested it. For the other five bags, the collection owners need to decide whether or not they will re-digitize the content.

VI. A SIDE-TRIP TO ARCHIVEMATICA

Shortly after the time Ohio State discovered the aforementioned issues, they also began looking at potentially replacing its pre-ingest and ingest workflow with Archivemata. [23] Working with Amazon Web Services the University Libraries established a test instance in the fall of 2024. [24] One of the appealing aspects of this potential solution is that Archivemata automates much of what the Libraries is already doing. Although automated, one can adapt the workflow to have human intervention at specific points, while delivering a similar AIP bagged package. In theory, this would compensate for the Libraries quality control issues, while potentially making it less onerous for its curatorial staff.

The toolset that Archivemata brings to bear, while somewhat similar, is vastly larger than what the University Libraries currently use. However, one key initial concern was that there is no native integration with Fedora; meaning that if the Libraries were to transfer bags to Fedora, it would lose all ability to see content from within Archivemata. Alternatively, Ohio State could have the AIPs land in an AWS S3 bucket, which could be monitored from Archivemata, although they would lose the added value of the Fedora preservation environment.

The University Libraries began testing just before the winter holidays in December 2024. Based upon the testing and discussions with established

Archivemata users, the Libraries have ultimately decided to no longer pursue it as a workflow replacement tool. Ohio State released its recommendations to internal stakeholders in early April 2025 and made the report publicly available later that month. [25] In summary, the reasons for no longer pursuing Archivemata are as follows:

- The PII detection is not robust enough even though it uses the same PII identification tool as Ohio State, Bulk Extractor.
- While Archivemata's Appraisal tab provides PII and file format analysis visualizations prior to ingest, it is only available there and is subsequently buried in the AIP making it difficult for future analysis; whereas since Ohio State creates that information prior to bagging, it already has set it aside for future analysis.
- The file preview function is an interesting feature in Archivemata that allows access to certain file types without having to launch another app; however, it is only available in the Appraisal tab and only previews images and audio-visual content limiting its overall usefulness.
- From a provenance perspective, Archivemata produces a copious amount of data logs, yet they are sometimes irrelevant, creating unnecessary clutter.
- SIPs, AIPs and DIPs are stored as UUID Quads, which creates unnecessarily complex and mostly empty directory structures. [26]
- The administrative dashboard had some interesting functionality, such as the ability to search across multiple AIPs; but in general it was no better than what Ohio State is currently doing.
- Finally, as previously noted, it does not inherently integrate with Fedora.

Ohio State has gone back to refining and tweaking its existing workflow. This is not meant to be an indictment of Archivemata. It is a powerful tool, and can be the solution for other institutions, especially ones that do not have the bandwidth for developing their own workflow; it is just not the correct fit for Ohio State's current needs.

VII. THE CONTINUING JOURNEY

Workflow development, much like digital preservation, is not a state that is achieved, but a continuous process looking for efficiencies, without sacrificing authenticity, learning from our mistakes and finding and developing better ways of doing things. It is a messy process. As such, Ohio State continue to work on revising and updating its workflow. The University Libraries have added the necessary quality assurance and control steps, including checking file counts prior to and after bagging, creating a checksum for the bag and verifying the checksum post ingest. Further, they have created a checklist that summarizes the workflow—which currently clocks in at nearly 100 pages in length—into a series of steps that should aid the curatorial staff in faithfully performing and documenting the workflow processes.

As Ohio State looks forward, they will be migrating its administrative dashboard from Microsoft Lists to Airtable, a more robust solution that will also allow Digital Preservation's workflows to be more holistically integrated with other workflows across the University Libraries. Additionally, they intend to consider and conduct testing of:

- alternative tools for PII identification;
- alternative tools for bagging as the Library of Congress will not be updating Bagger;
- tools for better audio-visual forensics;
- utilizing VMs (virtual machines) as replacement for the remote desktop processing workstations, which should provide greater stability and uptime;
- hardware and software tools to conduct digital object migrations from legacy media carriers.

From a broader perspective, Ohio State recently migrated to a new library catalog platform that has implications for linkages to digitized book content that is being preserved within the Gray Repo; additionally, within the next year Ohio State will migrate from Archivists' Toolkit to Access to Memory (AtoM) [27] for its finding aids platform.

A continuing challenge Ohio State has on this journey is maintaining workflow documentation. Each little change means having to update the

workflow documentation. It may include textual and/or visualization changes that can have a ripple effect throughout the whole of the document. This can be further exacerbated by having to redact portions of the workflow for cybersecurity reason, if they are to publicly share their work in an accessible manner for the greater good of the profession. The redacting process is the relatively easy and straightforward part; maintaining an accessible document is more difficult.

Finally, Ohio State needs to begin tracking information about retrieval and associated costs to better understand its total cost of ownership.

Digital preservation is a continuing journey; the roads and paths we take vary in quality from smooth pavement to muddy and rutted messes; accidents happen along the way, even when the road seems pristine and clear. It is how we learn from the mistakes and correct our course that make our journey more successful and our digital preservation programs more durable.

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Mr. Noonan, with 25 years of experience in the archives, records management and library professions, plays a key role in developing a trusted digital preservation ethos and infrastructure at The Ohio State University Libraries. He provides strategy, expertise, and leadership through close collaboration with faculty, staff, and other leaders in the University Libraries; and is a frequent contributor to the wider professional community.

